
Evaluating mRNA COVID-19 vaccine safety
and identifying potential causes of its side
effects

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Introduction & Background

mRNA vaccine is one of the newest vaccines on the market, and in use during the pandemic. Due to its novelty, research on its side effects has not been widely done.

And it is even harder to make a reasonable correlation between the adverse side effects and their causes.

These side effects greatly concern the public, which eventually causes vaccine hesitancy.

The aim of this project is to investigate the safety and side effects of the COVID-19 mRNA vaccine, compare that with the conventional vaccine through literature review, and propose potential causes of those side effects.

Methods

This project is purely based on literature review and using pre-existent data.

We collected data on severe and normal side effects of influenza and Pfizer mRNA vaccine and used to make a correlation between them.

Pfizer vaccine data are taken from the official CDC site, and influenza vaccine taken from the WHO and Single Care.

Results

Attenuated Virus Vaccine

5 in 1 million had anaphylaxis with Pfizer vaccine
 0.7 in 1 million had anaphylaxis with influenza vaccine

mRNA Vaccine

Common side effects	Since mRNA vaccines use genetic material and simulate the coronavirus infection, side effects such as fever could be due to the immune system's reaction.
Anaphylaxis	Hypersensitivity to Polyethylene glycol (PEG) might cause anaphylaxis.

Discussion

From the comparison, we can deduce that Pfizer vaccine is close to or less than the possibility of side effects to influenza vaccine, with an exception of pain at injection site. While adverse events such as anaphylaxis, it occurred more among Pfizer recipients. Possibilities of potential causes could be due to immune reaction or Hypersensitivity of Polyethylene glycol.

Acknowledgements and Future Research

This project is supported by Rapidynamic Lab.

To investigate potential causes of side effects, we plan to design an experiment to test out each major component of the Pfizer vaccine. We will test out each major component on a controlled group (healthy) and experimental group of mice (one type of allergy).

References

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